

Studies in Sulphur Compounds. Preparation of Aromatic Sulphides and Oxidation of Some Sulphides to Sulphones

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2,2'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-dinitro-5,5'-diacetyl diphenyl sulphide (I) and 2,2'-dihydroxy-5,5'-dipropionyl diphenyl sulphide (II) have been prepared and their constitutions proved by nitration. 2,2'-Dihydroxy-4,4'-diacetyl, 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-diacetyl, 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy, 3,3'-diacetyl-4,6,4',6'-tetrahydroxy, 2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-dinitro-5,5'-diacetyl, 2,2'-dihydroxy-5,5'-dipropionyl, and 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-dipropionyl diphenyl sulphides have been oxidised with hydrogen peroxide in acetone to the corresponding sulphones.

When 3-nitro-4-hydroxyacetophenone and *p*-hydroxypropiophenone are allowed to react with thionyl chloride in presence of copper or with sulphur dichloride, sulphides (I) and (II) are obtained respectively. Sulphide (I) on nitration with concentrated nitric acid in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid affords picric acid. Of the three nitro groups present in picric acid, the one, *ortho* to -OH, was present originally in the sulphide molecule. The nitro group, *para* to -OH, has obviously replaced the original ketonic group^{1,4}. The third nitro group, which is *ortho* to OH, must have replaced the sulphur atom. Hence it is concluded that the two aromatic nuclei are joined through the sulphur atom in position *ortho* to -OH and *meta* to -COEt and -NO₂ groups in sulphide (I).

On nitration with nitric acid, sulphide (II) furnished 3-nitro-4-hydroxypropiophenone. Hence it is concluded that the two aromatic nuclei in sulphide (II) are joined through the sulphur atom in position *meta* to -COEt and *ortho* to -OH groups.

Of the oxidising agents³⁻⁷ used, hydrogen peroxide in acetic acid or acetone is found to be the best as it does not attack groups other than the sulphide. These products of oxidation are different from those obtained by the action of thionyl chloride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride where sulphoxides⁸⁻⁹ are obtained; hence these have been assigned the sulphone constitution.

EXPERIMENTAL

2,2'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-dinitro-5,5'-diacetyl Diphenyl Sulphide (I).—Thionyl chloride (5 ml) was added to an intimate mixture of 3-nitro-4-hydroxyacetophenone (1 g.) and

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4. Wood and Travis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2405.
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7. Kulkarni and Jadhav, *this Journal*, 1957, **34**, 245.
8. Smiles and Bain, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 1118.
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copper (1 g.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature and then refluxed on a boiling water bath for about half an hour. On removing excess of thionyl chloride by acetone extraction and the solvent from the extract, a black mass was obtained. It was washed repeatedly with CS_2 and acetic acid. It did not melt up to 300° . (Found: S, 8.00. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6N_2S$ requires S, 8.16%). The *diacetate* did not melt up to 300° . (Found: S, 6.51. $C_{20}H_{16}O_{10}N_2S$ requires S, 6.72%). The 2,4-DNP did not melt up to 300° . (Found: S, 4.32. $C_{28}H_{20}O_{14}N_2S$ requires S, 4.25%).

2,4,6-Trinitrophenol.—Sulphide (I) (0.5 g.) was added to a mixture of HNO_3 (conc., 15 ml) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 15 ml) which was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Next day it was heated on a boiling water bath for about 15 minutes, allowed to cool, and then diluted with ice-water. The solution was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution furnished a yellow substance which melted at 120° . It gave tests for nitrogen but did not give any test for sulphur. It showed undepressed m.p. when admixed with a genuine specimen of picric acid.

2,2'-Dihydroxy-5,5'-dipropionyl Diphenyl Sulphide (II).—Thionyl chloride (5 ml) was added to an intimate mixture of *p*-hydroxypropiophenone (1 g.) and copper powder (1 g.). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The mass was extracted with chloroform. A red paste was obtained on removal of the solvent. It was repeatedly washed with CS_2 and finally treated with alkali when it dissolved, forming a red solution which was filtered. On acidifying, a yellow mass separated which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 103° . It is highly soluble in ethanol and ether, sparingly soluble in chloroform, and insoluble in CS_2 and benzene. (Found: S, 9.50. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4S$ requires S, 9.69%).

The same sulphide (II) was obtained by the interaction of *p*-hydroxypropiophenone and sulphur dichloride. The *diacetate* was prepared by boiling it with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine; m.p. $98-98^\circ$. (Found: S, 7.81. $C_{22}H_{22}O_6S$ requires S, 7.72%). The 2,4-DNP melted at 125° . (Found: S, 4.71. $C_{30}H_{26}O_{10}N_2S$ requires S, 4.63%).

TABLE I

Diphenyl sulphone.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.
2,2'-Dihydroxy-5,5'-diacetyl	> 300°	$C_{16}H_{14}O_6S$	9.41	9.58
2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-diacetyl	104°	$C_{18}H_{16}O_6S$	8.84	8.84
3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy	189°	$C_{16}H_{14}O_6S$	9.34	9.58
3,3'-Diacetyl-4,6,4',6'-tetrahydroxy	185°	$C_{16}H_{14}O_6S$	8.51	8.74
2,2'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-dinitro-5,5'-diacetyl	135°	$C_{16}H_{14}O_{10}N_2S$	7.65	7.54
2,2'-Dihydroxy-5,5'-dipropionyl	105°	$C_{18}H_{16}O_6S$	8.76	8.84
	(decomp.)			
2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-dipropionyl	165°	$C_{20}H_{18}O_6S$	8.31	8.20

3-Nitro-4-hydroxypropiophenone.—Sulphide (II) (1 g.) was added to a mixture of HNO_3 (conc., 5 ml) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 5 ml). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Next day it was diluted with water when a yellowish white

solid separated. It was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 58-80°. It showed no lowering in m.p. when mixed with a genuine specimen¹⁰.

Preparation of Sulphones.—Hydrogen peroxide (20 ml) (100 vols.) was added to a solution of the sulphide (1 g.) in acetone (30 ml). The mixture was shaken well and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The sulphone usually separated which was filtered and washed with acetone. The yield was 0.8 g. (approx.) in all cases. The results are recorded in Table I.

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